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Technical note

Impaired intrinsic hand strength in women with osteoarthritis

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Background

Hand force assessment of patients is usually reduced to cylindrical and pinch grip force, evaluating extrinsic and intrinsic muscles altogether. These data are not sensitive enough to detect intrinsic deficits caused by pathologies such as hand osteoarthritis (HOA).^{1–3} Loss of intrinsic muscle strength may severely impair the hand function.² The Rotterdam intrinsic hand myometer (RIHM) enables friendly-use measurements of intrinsic forces with good reliability.^{2,4–7} The resistance is given by pulling on different angles over different hand segments, enabling strength measures of the muscles innervated by the median nerve, ulnar nerve, and combined median and ulnar nerves. This method is considered the best to test intrinsic strength.⁸ Despite being the recommended method to obtain intrinsic forces, it is unusual for clinics to own the RIHM due to commercial unavailability. In addition, there is a lack of data for intrinsic muscle strength in people with HOA. This work aims to evaluate the intrinsic fingers forces in women with HOA using a modified dynamometer emulating RIHM,⁹ and compare them to those of healthy participants, to identify intrinsic muscle deficits. A preliminary test was performed to check the validity of the modified dynamometer by comparing lumbrical forces measured with the modified dynamometer and with the Jamar dynamometer (Biometrics, Ltd) as gold standard. Then intrinsic forces of patients and healthy people were

analyzed: firstly, intrasession error and the effect of fatigue were studied; secondly, force data were computed, and the effect of sample characteristics (HOA or biological sex) was studied; and finally, the force reduction in HOA sample and the most affected joint movements and grasps are analyzed, providing an outline of the effect that intrinsic hand strength deficits may have on hand function.

Methods

Healthy sample (sample H): 27 subjects free of hand pathologies (13 healthy women 40 ± 9 years, sample H_w, and 14 healthy men 45 ± 8 years, sample H_m, 25 right-handed). Sample of pathologic women (sample P_w): 27 right-handed women with HOA (73 ± 8 years). Patients were recruited by clinicians from among hospital patients with symptoms, most of them diagnosed by image and all clinically confirmed according to Altman et al.¹⁰ Healthy participants were asymptomatic, female under 60 years. All the participants signed written consent, approved by the Jaume I University/Research Ethics Committee with Human Beings (CD/27/2022).

Intrinsic forces were measured in both samples using a dynamometer (Mecmesin CFG+200N) with a belt handle, simulating the RIHM, although with less ergonomic manufacturing finishes. The participants, seated with their elbow resting on a table, performed maximal force in five different isolated hand joint motions² and three grasp types (with an important role of intrinsic muscles) with their dominant hand (Fig. 1), three times each, with 30 seconds in-between for recovery. The lumbrical grasp force was also measured with the Jamar (Biometrics, Ltd).

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Fig. 1. Force measurements performed in five joint movements² and three grasp types. IA = index abduction; IF = index flexion; T, F = thumb flexion; TA = thumb abduction; LA = little finger abduction; P2F = pinch with 2 fingers; LP = lateral pinch; L = lumbrical.

Analyses

Preliminary test to check the validity of the modified dynamometer: a repeated measures ANOVA per sample (healthy participants and patients with HOA) was conducted, with lumbrical force (mean value from three repetitions) as the dependent variable and the device used (Jamar/emulated RIHM) as the factor.

Intrasection repeatability: computed as the root-mean-squared error in a set of ANOVAs (one per force type and sample), with force as dependent variable and participant as factor.¹¹

Table 1

Intrasection errors for measurements recorded with the adapted Mecmesin dynamometer in Newton and in percentage related to mean value

	Units	Intrasection error							
		IA	IF	TF	LA	TA	P2F	LP	L
HOA patients	N	2.67	3.52	5.42	2.47	2.75	4.43	4.56	6.65
	%	12%	12%	16%	15%	12%	13%	15%	14%
Healthy participants	N	6.38	4.62	7.42	5.41	4.24	6.77	5.44	9.52
	%	14%	9%	10%	16%	11%	15%	10%	12%

Force measurements labeled as detailed in Figure 1.

HOA = handosteo arthritis; IA = index abduction; IF = index flexion; TF = thumb flexion; TA = thumb abduction; LA = little finger abduction; P2F = pinch with two fingers; LP = lateral pinch; L = lumbrical.

Fatigue effect on maximal force: assessed with a set of ANOVAs (one per force type and sample), with force as dependent variable and repetition as factor.

Characterization data: maximal forces in the three repetitions were averaged (F_{av}), and statistics computed.

Biological sex effect: assessed with a set of ANOVAs (one per force type) on sample H, with F_{av} as dependent variable and biological sex as factor.

HOA effect: assessed with a set of ANOVAs (one per force type) with F_{av} as dependent variable and samples P_w and H_w as factor. Also, for each female patient, the percentiles of the F_{av} values per force type as if belonging to sample H_w were computed.

Findings

The modified dynamometer had good reliability when compared to the Jamar dynamometer. No significant differences were found from the repeated measures ANOVA.

Repeatability of the measurement method is good, given the low intrasection errors obtained (Table 1). No fatigue effects were observed, as the repetition was not significant ($p > 0.05$), neither for the healthy sample nor for the patients.

Biological sex showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) across all force types in the ANOVAs conducted on healthy participants. Women's forces in all force types were significantly lower in sample with HOA, except for pinch, bold marked in Table 2, with a mean decrease of 30% (detailed in Table 3 for each force type).

Discussion

Good reliability of the modified dynamometer has been demonstrated by comparing the forces obtained in lumbrical grasp to those obtained with the Jamar dynamometer. Jamar dynamometry is a well-known gold standard for cylindrical grip measure, and previous studies have confirmed the validity of this device for measuring lumbrical grasp.¹² In addition, and reinforcing the validation of the modified dynamometer, mean forces for both healthy males and females (Table 2) were consistent with those reported using the RIHM.⁵ Healthy sample size and age difference between female samples are limitations of this work. Regarding the size of the healthy sample, despite having a threshold of potential type II error of 30%, which is above the traditionally accepted threshold of 20%,^{13,14} significant differences were found. Concerning age samples, it is not easy to guarantee a matched sample of female with 70 years mean age free of HOA without using imaging diagnosis.¹⁵ It is worth mentioning that previous work showed that the reduction in grip strength suffered by patients with HOA may be due to degenerative diseases over and above age.¹¹ Haugen et al¹⁶ showed that women with HOA older than 60 years had only a slight reduction in cylindrical grip strength compared to healthy women, while at younger ages the reduction was close to 25%. Considering the

Table 2
Mean force and SD in each measurement by biological sex

		Statistic	Force (N)							
			IA	IF	TF	LA	TA	P2F	LP	L
HOA patients	W	Mean	22.20	27.56	33.23	15.67	22.41	33.34	29.17	44.99
		SD	4.72	8.05	12.82	4.18	8.48	9.96	10.28	15.20
Healthy participants	W	Mean	35.82	38.80	52.09	22.32	32.60	35.51	41.09	61.99
		SD	10.02	10.70	17.10	5.91	6.89	7.35	11.57	18.96
	M	Mean	56.93	67.39	91.97	44.41	47.47	51.40	67.59	100.80
		SD	17.57	22.39	30.16	21.06	14.39	16.80	20.67	38.47

Force measurements labeled as detailed in Figure 1. Statistically significant differences between HOA and healthy women marked in bold.

HOA = hand osteoarthritis; IA = index abduction; IF = index flexion; TF = thumb flexion; TA = thumb abduction; LA = little finger abduction; P2F = pinch with two fingers; LP = lateral pinch; L = lumbrical.

Table 3
Force decrease of HOA women in each measurement compared to healthy women

Force decrease (%) of mean force values (HOA patients to healthy women) in right hand							
IA	IF	TF	LA	TA	P2F	LP	L
38%	29%	36%	30%	31%	6%	29%	27%

Force measurements labeled as detailed in Figure 1.

HOA = hand osteoarthritis; IA = index abduction; IF = index flexion; TF = thumb flexion; TA = thumb abduction; LA = little finger abduction; P2F = pinch with two fingers; LP = lateral pinch; L = lumbrical.

inclusion criteria for healthy elder women and that the prevalence of HOA in those over 60 years is close to 70%, the reduction in strength commonly assigned to women due to age could be due to the disease.

This work provides intrinsic hand forces data from a sample of 27 women with HOA, with no such data having been reported previously in this pathology, which indicates that HOA affects women intrinsic hand forces. Movements more likely affected are those corresponding to thumb flexion and index abduction. Grasp types requiring thumb flexion (lateral pinch, oblique, and lumbrical) or those requiring index abduction (spherical grasp or intermediate pinch) would be consequently affected, which is in accordance with previous works.¹¹ These grasps affecting thumb flexion are required in tasks such as opening jars/bottles or serving from a carton, and grasps affecting index abduction are required in tasks such as using cutlery, actions in which patients have previously reported problems.¹⁷ This work provides relevant information to clinicians and therapists, as beyond the known degeneration and swelling in the joints of the pathology, it offers insight into which movements and grips are affected. Further research remains to be done to identify specific potential targets for therapeutic interventions such as specific exercises and before intrinsic force recording can be considered as a testing procedure in the clinical setting. Standard dynamometers could be adapted in a simple way, enabling the measurement of intrinsic forces. Information on the adaptation performed in this work can be obtained from the authors upon justified request.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing

interests: Regional Government (grant numbers GV/2020/067 and CIGE/2021/024) and Universitat Jaume I (UJI-A2021-03).

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JHT Read for Credit

JHT 37 # 4 Quiz: # B15

Record your answers on the Return Answer Form found on the tear-out coupon at the back of this issue. There is only one best answer for each question.

- #1. The RHIM is not commonly used clinically due primarily to
- cost considerations
 - commercial unavailability
 - its unreliability
 - its difficulty to administer
- #2. Subjects were
- volunteer member of local hospital therapy departments
 - all normals
 - all actual patients
 - both normals and actual patients
- #3. Validity was established by applying
- an ICC
 - standard deviations
 - an ANOVA
 - Student T Test
- #4. Forces were expressed as the _____ of repeated efforts
- median
 - mean
 - mode
 - none of the above
- #5. The instrument proved to be reliable
- true
 - false